

Semantic Data Modeling for the Census Database

Deliverable 2 - Documented Semantic Data Model

This deliverable entailed creating an explicit semantic reference data model for the Census data and relevant art historical data more generally. Using CIDOC CRM and its extensions as well as the SARI Semantic Reference Data Model modeling strategy, this deliverable created a robust documentation of a full semantic reference data model for the Census project. The result is the Semantic Census Data Models.

The Census Semantic Data Models (CSDM) represent a coherent set of semantically-encoded data models for the use of art historians in the (re-)representation of art historical data related to the history of monuments, the documents that respond to or bear witness to them, the people or places that relate to these objects of study through historical events, and the images and bibliography which reference them.

The result of this work can be consulted at:

<https://census-antiquity-renaissance.github.io/census-csdm/>

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